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Coordination Complexes of Paludrine with Ferrous Sulphate and Cobalt Chloride

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IN continuation of our work^{1,2} on the metal complexes of antimalarials, herein we describe iron and cobalt complexes of paludrine. The object in view is to see if these complexes may serve a double purpose of being antimalarial and at the same time antianaemic.

Experimental :

Paludrine recrystallised m.p. 129° (lit. 130°), ferrous sulphate E.P. and cobalt chloride A.R.

Conductivity measurements :

Conductivity measurements of (i) Ferrous sulphate-Paludrine in 80% methanol and (ii) Cobalt chloride-Paludrine in 80% ethanol were carried out at 20° using 'Toshniwal' conductivity bridge and dip type electrodes. 10 ml. of the ligand was diluted to 200 ml. and titrated against the metal solution. After the volume corrections, the results are plotted in Fig. 1, which indicate 2:1 complex formation.

Isolation :

(a) Paludrine base 1.5 g. (2 mole) was dissolved in methyl alcohol while ferrous sulphate 0.8 g. (1

mole) in the same solvent containing 2 drops of sulphuric acid to stabilize the divalent iron. Base

Fig. 1. Metal salt = 0.01 M : Ligand = 0.005 M ; t = 20°.

solution was added slowly to the ferrous sulphate solution with constant stirring. At first no change was observed but after some time the solution became turbid more and more. On cooling in an ice bath for several hours, a brick red complex separated, which was filtered, washed with methyl alcohol and dried in vacuum; yield 1.0 g, m.p. 200°.

(b) Paludrine base 1.5 g (2 mole) and cobalt chloride 0.7 g. (1 mole) were dissolved separately in minimum quantities of absolute alcohol. Paludrine solution was added slowly to the cobalt chloride solution and cooled in an ice bath for 4 hrs. The colour of the solution changed from dark blue to reddish brown and no complex separated. It was refluxed for 3 hrs on water bath with water condenser. The reddish brown colloidal solution changed to blue. It was cooled and the excess of solvent evaporated on water bath. The complex was filtered, washed with ether and dried; yield 1.1 gms., m.p. 280° d.

Analysis :

Iron was estimated by cupferron³ as oxide. Cobalt was estimated as tetrapyrindine-cobalt-dithionate⁴ after removing the base and nitrogen by modified

TABLE I

Composition of the complex	percentages	Fe/Co	SO ₄ /Cl	N	H ₂ O
(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₅ Cl) ₂ .FeSO ₄ .2H ₂ O	Found	7.82	13.14	19.14	5.40
	Requires	8.03	13.82	20.14	5.18
(C ₁₁ H ₁₆ N ₅ Cl) ₂ .CoCl ₂ .2H ₂ O	Found	8.24	9.70	20.20	4.72
	Requires	8.76	10.54	20.81	5.34

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Kjeldahl's method⁵. Chloride, sulphate and water were estimated by usual methods.

The analytical results for paludrine-ferrous sulphate and paludrine-cobalt chloride complexes are given in Table I.

Discussion :

Considering the biguanidino structure (I) for paludrine, the complex formation will take place through the guanidino group

rather than the chlorophenyl group of the molecule. The conductometric titration results plotted in Fig. 1 clearly indicate that paludrine form 2:1 complexes with ferrous sulphate and cobalt chloride. The analytical results correspond to analogous compositions e.g. $(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{Cl})_2\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_5\text{Cl})_2\text{CoCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ respectively. It is therefore expected that they will have similar structures as given in (II)

(II) Where M = Fe or Co
and X₂ = SO₄ or Cl₂

Structure (II) is supported by the work of Ray *et al*^{6,7} who have studied transition metal complexes of biguanides and have assigned the structure (III) to the four coordination complexes.

Ghosh and Banerjee⁸ have given similar structure to *p*-anisoyl biguanide complexes of bivalent metals. Spacu⁹ has also described copper halide complex of paludrine having composition $[(\text{Paludrine})_2\text{Cu}]\text{X}_2$.

Structure (II) is further supported by the I.R. absorption bands (which will form part of a later communication) of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{-NH}^+$ group at 1290 and 1280 cm^{-1} in iron and cobalt complexes. The characteristic absorption bands of -NH_2 are observed at 1735 ± 5 and $2910 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively. Coordinated water in these complexes is indicated by absorption bands at 815, 1650 and 3400 cm^{-1} .

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Cadmium (II) Complexes with 4-Cyanopyridine

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AS a part of investigations on nitrogen bonded complexes of *d*¹⁰ metals, several complexes of cadmium (II) and zinc (II) have been reported¹⁻⁵ with substituted pyridines and quinolines. This communication describes some cadmium complexes of the general formula $[\text{CdL}_2\text{X}_2]$ where L is 4-cyanopyridine and X is Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and NCS⁻. The ligand 4-cyanopyridine has been chosen because it has been reported earlier that cyanopyridines may coordinate either through pyridine nitrogen or through nitrile nitrogen.

Experimental :

All the chemicals used were of *AnalaR* quality. The compounds were prepared in ethanolic medium by reacting cadmium salts, CdX_2 where X is Cl⁻, Br⁻, I⁻ and NCS⁻ and the ligand in 1 : 2 ratio. There